

Potential of Sweet Orange Peel Extract (*Citrus sinensis* L. Osbeck) as Anti-Obesity in Male White Rats

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Obesity is closely related to the scientific field of animal physiology, where obesity is a condition when there is an accumulation of fat in the body which then affects or even inhibits the work of the body's organs. The problem of obesity is currently receiving serious attention in the world of health. The prevalence of obesity worldwide has increased drastically in the last decade. In Indonesia itself, the results of Basic Health Research in 2018 showed the incidence of obesity increased from 13.9% in 2007 to 21.8% in 2018 (Riskeudas, 2018). One of the obesity treatments, namely using chemical drugs, is known to have long-term side effects on its users. Against the background of the long-term side effects of using chemical drugs for obese patients, made the author interested in studying one of the natural anti-obesity potentials, namely sweet orange peel (*Citrus sinensis* L. Osbeck). Sweet orange peel is known to have high flavonoid content. Many studies have been conducted on the benefits of citrus fruits as anti-obesity agents, but based on scientific literature searches, the utilization of sweet orange peel waste (garbage) as an anti-obesity agent (*Citrus sinensis* L. Osbeck) and its effect on body weight, appetite and cholesterol levels in male white rats induced by high fat diet. By combining the scientific fields of animal physiology with biochemistry, the authors hope the emergence of new research results that can be utilized by the public as an effort to reduce the risk of long-term side effects of chemical treatment of obesity diseases and reduce the rate of obese people in Indonesia.

Obesity is an abnormal or excessive fat accumulation that poses a risk to health (WHO, 2016). The causes of obesity are multifactorial, but the imbalance between calories consumed and expended is the main cause of obesity. This imbalance results in the accumulation of excess energy in adipocyte cells which if it occurs continuously for a long time can cause cells to experience hypertrophy and hyperplasia. The increase in body fat mass results in an increase in adipocyte cell size (hypertrophy) and an increase in the number of fat cells. This increase in the number of fat cells is closely related to intracellular adipocyte dysfunction, as well as stress on the endoplasmic reticulum and mitochondria (Kim et al., 2013). This causes abnormal adipocyte production and free fatty acids (FFA)

to occur along with inflammatory markers. If the adipocyte dysfunction that occurs is more severe, the clinical manifestations and comorbid obesity that occur will also be more pronounced (Kumar & Kelly, 2016). Inflammation of the control centers of eating and body metabolism in the hypothalamus, especially in the arcuate nucleus (ARC) and paraventricular nucleus (PVN) can be triggered by high fat and sugar intake (Santoso et al., 2021). Vogt et al. in Santoso & Rita (2019) stated that this will have an impact on dysregulation of energy homeostasis, insulin resistance, dyslipidemia and hyperglycemia. the clinical manifestations and comorbid obesity that occur will also be more real (Kumar & Kelly, 2016). Inflammation of the control centers of eating and body metabolism in the hypothalamus, especially in the arcuate nucleus (ARC) and paraventricular nucleus (PVN) can be triggered by high fat and sugar intake (Santoso et al., 2021). Vogt et al. in Santoso & Rita (2019) stated that this will have an impact on dysregulation of energy homeostasis, insulin resistance, dyslipidemia and hyperglycemia. the clinical manifestations and comorbid obesity that occur will also be more real (Kumar & Kelly, 2016). Inflammation of the control centers of eating and body metabolism in the hypothalamus, especially in the arcuate nucleus (ARC) and paraventricular nucleus (PVN) can be triggered by high fat and sugar intake (Santoso et al., 2021). Vogt et al. in Santoso & Rita (2019) stated that this will have an impact on dysregulation of energy homeostasis, insulin resistance, dyslipidemia and hyperglycemia.

Jaerony in Yanis, et al. (2020) stated that the use of plant materials as natural medicine is believed to be quite effective and safe because it rarely causes side effects and the price is relatively cheaper. The plants used usually contain flavonoids, tannins, glycosides, saponins, steroids, and essential oils which are strong antioxidant compounds (Linder, 2006). Sweet orange is one of the most popular types of citrus in Indonesia. The skin of this fruit contains phenolic components such as pectin, tannins, flavonoid compounds such as hesperidin, narirutin and nobiletin, as well as volatile compounds such as terpenes, sesquiterpenes, aldehydes, catechins, esters and sterols. This flavonoid in orange peel can increase levels of the hormone cholecystokinin (CCK) in endocrine cells in the small intestine which helps in controlling food intake (Rafiq et al, 2018). The content of narirutin and hesperidin in sweet orange peel can absorb the stimulus in lipolysis and reduce the accumulation of triglycerides in adipose tissue and reduce fatty acid synthesis (Parkar, 2016). Catechins can be used to lower cholesterol, LDL and triglyceride levels by increasing lipoprotein lipase activity, so that the catabolism of triglyceride-rich lipoproteins such as VLDL (Very Low-Density Lipoprotein) and IDL (Intermediate

Density Lipoprotein) increases. HDL (High Density Lipoprotein) cholesterol levels will increase indirectly due to a decrease in VLDL triglyceride levels. The effect of lowering LDL cholesterol is thought to be related to increased clearance of VLDL and IDL in the liver so that LDL production decreases (Frinanda et al., 2014). Sitompul in Frinanda et al.

Several relevant studies on the anti-obesity effect of orange peel and the content of compounds contained in orange peel have been carried out, including research conducted by Kamel et al in 2019 which stated that a dose of 800 mg/kg BW of tangerine peel extract could reduce body mass. Index (BMI), % body fat, waist circumference, total cholesterol and triglycerides in adolescents aged 10-19 years. Research by Xiong H et al in 2019 stated that giving hesperidin 25 mg/day for 12 weeks could increase fat metabolism and reduce total cholesterol in male Wistar strain rats fed a high fat diet (Xiong H et al., 2019). Research conducted by Samsudin R et al in 2017 stated that giving Pacitan sweet orange peel water extract at a dose of 500 mg/kg and 750 mg/kg BW for 6 weeks could significantly reduce body weight, total cholesterol, LDL cholesterol and triglycerides compared to control group (Samsudin et al, 2017). Shin et al in 2013 suggested that giving hesperidin a dose of 0.07 mg/kg BW of mice for 9 weeks could reduce body weight, total body fat and serum lipids in mice fed a high fat diet (Shin et al., 2013). The use of orange peel as an anti-obesity drug will be useful and safe if it is used by considering at least six aspects of accuracy, one of which is the right dose.

Sweet orange peel can be used as a natural anti-obesity to reduce the risk of side effects using chemical drugs, because of the content of pectin, tannins, flavonoids such as hesperidin, narirutin and nobiletin, as well as volatile content such as terpenes, sesquiterpene aldehydes, catechins, esters and sterols in it. can increase levels of the hormone cholecystokinin (CCK), reduce the accumulation of triglycerides, and lower cholesterol, LDL and triglyceride levels in the body. The use of this sweet orange peel will be useful and safe if used with the right dose.

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